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Codes, heterogeneities, and structures: Visual information and visual art

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Abstract: Codes are mechanisms in which signs are actualized. They relate various sign sides to each other. These sign sides can be represented as heterogeneities (diversity, relations, differences), some are organized with the help of various differences – identities formulated in a specific way. The basis of the codes of visual perception and art are primarily the heterogeneities of the elements perceived directly (contours of objects, sizes, directions of movement, light and color irritants, etc.). A structure, conceived of as a manner of connection, is a principle for constructing a kind of a whole and is the center of an organized heterogeneity.

Keywords: codes; heterogeneities; structures; perception; sign systems; visual art

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With the widest approach, signs and signs systems form the basis of all living processes (Sebeok 1999). As it has been shown in various research, signs do not exist regardless of codes. Visual information is produced due to perceptive codes of visual perception (Hall 1980; Nichols 1981; Eco 1982; Fiske 1989). Repeated actions of various codes are organized in their interrelations in the systematicities of languages and cultures (Danesi 1994: 18; Danesi 1999: 29). This idea makes one first turn to key codes that enable the production of visual information and communication in visual art.

There are many models of codes and their relations with signs in semiotics (Nöth 1998: 206–220). Some relations of codes and signs are regarded here. First, it is necessary to specify the connection between codes and signs. Codes are *mechanisms in which signs are actualized* (Jacobson 1971; Eco 1976; Hoffmeyer and Emmeche 1991). They relate various sign sides to each other (Chandler 1994). In the sign model by Charles S. Peirce, *codes* can be represented as *connections of sign sides: the connection of representamens with objects, interpretants*, other representamens (Figure 1a). These sign sides can be represented as heterogeneities (diversity, relations, differences), some are organized with the help of various differences – identities in a specific way (Figure 1b). As is known, Peirce considered representamen as a synonym of sign. When using the concept of

Fig. 1: Interrelations of semiotic triangles in the processes of semiosis. a. Modification of models of triangle sign (O – object, I – interpretant, R – representamen) and semiosis (by Lang 1993; Hoffman 2001; Ponzio 2005). b. Heterogeneities (H) in a model of sign.

representamen, more attention is given to a signifier. Due to the organization of these heterogeneities, codes are actualized in information processes. This corresponds to the idea of difference as the basis of information (Ashby 1956; Ursul 1971), difference – identity as the basis of language (Saussure 1959), translation of differences and identities from some layers of thinking to others (Quine 1973).

The basis of codes of visual perception and art are primarily the heterogeneities of the elements perceived directly (contours of objects, sizes, directions of movement, light and color irritants, etc.). The idea of directly perceived visual elements and relations answers the semiotic ideas of the figure level (Prieto 1964), the signal level (Milewskii 1965; Sharov 1999). This idea corresponds to semiotics (Jameson 1972: 152; Hall 1980; Bignell 1997) and also to the neurophysiological models describing irritants as the basis of codes (Somjen 1972). The heterogeneities on which codes “rely upon” are not confined to the level of signals and their structures. Codes “rely upon” heterogeneities at all levels of sign systems, including the levels of ideas, ethical standards, and aesthetic values. These levels have their own heterogeneities that organize their differences – identities, structures. As the heterogeneities are organized at these different levels, codes are also actualized at them. This corresponds to the definition of codes as mechanisms that link the planes of expression and planes of content by L. Hjelmslev (1961). The relations of the signified and the signifier forming the planes of expression and the planes of content create various levels. This corresponds to the model, according to which the signified and the signifier (the planes of content and expression) in sign systems seem to build over each other in various dimensions thus forming languages, styles, and other stable systematicities in structural concep-

tion (Barthes 1965) and its interpretation (Stepanov 1975). This answers the idea of codes as mechanisms connecting the governing systems and the governed ones (Hoffmeyer and Emmeche 1991; Hoffmeyer 1996). The idea of culture as a code system is also linked with the previous one (Danesi 1999).

It may be stated that code mechanisms presuppose the organization of heterogeneities on which they rely. This arrangement can be viewed in compliance with the idea of the form of the content plane and the expression plane by L. Hjelmslev. The author prefers regarding the organization of this or that plane as connections “differences-identities” actualized in the relations of element groups according to certain features. Relying on the experience of describing visual objects (Somov 1975), it can be noted that with the use of this detailed approach, one can single out the following *key universals of organizing heterogeneities: differential features, differences-identities, elements, structures, systems* (Figure 2).

A structure as a way of connection, a principle of constructing a kind of a whole is the center of heterogeneity organization. This corresponds to the conceptions of structuralism in which the central organizing role of structures is admitted, which was illustrated in various research of a methodological nature (Ivanov 2008). The structures of sign systems are actualized due to codes, which answers the general interpretation of codes as the key mechanisms of life (Hoffmeyer and Emmeche 1991). Codes are actualized in physical carriers (at the levels of neurons, interneuronic networks, carriers of a different physical nature; Somjen 1972; Pribram 1971; Chernigovskaya 1999). On this basis, transformations of structures are carried

Fig. 2: Heterogeneities (H) of representaments (R). H₁ – heterogeneity differentiated by interpretants, H₂ – differentiated by objects, H₃ – differentiated by other representaments. Heterogeneity includes: Sys – system; St – structure; Id – identity; F – features; El – elements; D – difference, RI – relation.

out. Some of them are well studied in the course of production of visual sensor information with the help of codes (Somjen 1972). In particular, such are the codes of identifying location and distance between the objects, their size, location of an observer, on the basis of summing up the signals (their structures). The information about space and moving of a communicant in it is created on the basis of such structural transformations. These structural characteristics are formed as a result of summation of the more elementary characteristics (brightness, textures, borders of objects, etc.) by codes (Somjen 1972).

Codes “allow” translating certain structures, provide their isomorphism (transfer) or interaction (integration). Codes and structures are actualized in differences-identities in various perception processes. Distinctness (clearness) of structures is vitally important for the regulation of “organism – environment.” Structures (as principles of construction, ways of connecting elements of the whole) (Toda and Shuford 1965; Il’in 1972; Somov 1990, 2007; Barbyshev and Somov 1990) are important in cognitive processes including those of visual information and art. Relativism partly impedes such (ontological) understanding. The followers of the neo-positivistic approach proved the arbitrariness of structure establishment in semiotic research (Martinet 1962). The methodological origin of the key structures is shown in semiotics (Eco 1968). At the same time, structures are different and some of them have ontological aspects that become especially evident in the course of analysis of artworks. Dividing an image into squares (as if they are imposed on an image), for instance, can provide some information about it. Taking the aspect ratio of a square image as a basis will provide both a structure that is convenient for analysis and a proportion of a frame at which a spectator looks and that limits the image with a frame. As analysis of some masterpieces of visual art shows, aspect ratio of such a square is an important structure. Main figures, heads, and faces of the depicted people fit the squares geometrically similar to the image field (Somov 2005). Otherwise stated, some structures are only methods of depiction, while the others are elements of codes materialized in sign systems. It is vital that the whole range of various structures (proportions, rhythms, symmetries, topological universals, numbers of elements, etc.) is actualized in code mechanisms. The idea of multiple structures taking part in visual perception is closely connected with cognitive sciences, primarily with the key ideas of Gestalt psychology. According to a number of theories, interconnections of various structures are the basis of thinking processes (by Eysenck’s conception). Structures are manifested in rather diverse signs and intellectual processes (logical thinking, perception, invention, playing, etc.). Various structures are manifested in the sign systems of IQ tests most clearly. The structures of sign systems of artworks are something similar to those tests. These or those structures can be seen in the key groups of relations and elements of works,

which the author tended to show in the course of semiotic analysis of art masterpieces (Somov 2005, 2008). Code interrelations and structural transformations are carried out in the thinking activity on the whole. These interrelations are most obvious in design. Thus, to arrange the space of various life processes, to solve the task of equal distribution of efforts in a construction and unify the processes of construction production, a designer has to single out: 1) structures of the arranged space; 2) structures of a constructive system; 3) structures of the processes of delivery and mounting the elements of these constructions (Somov 1990). Each group of structures (1, 2, and 3) is connected with the structures of the other two groups. Correspondingly, the mechanisms connecting various types of structures are formed (Barbyshev and Somov 1972). Codes in various thinking processes function in the same way, which is confirmed by the research in which models of interconnection of structures are suggested as the basis of describing the thinking activity (Voronin et al. 1982). Structure participation in the thinking activity is most obvious in IQ texts by Eysenck, which have their origin in Gestalt psychology. One or several interrelated structures that have to be differentiated (numerical, topological, linguistic, etc.) serve to solve intellectual tasks. The ability to differentiate and integrate structures unites such tasks. According to their role in cognitive processes, structures are the basis of efficient organization of visual information, the basis of the “right” perception. In addition, the presence of structures in art masterpieces is explained by the participation of a brain activity mechanism connecting the emotions of pleasure with thinking in the processes of perception. Otherwise stated, thinking activity is supported by positive emotions, which is demonstrated in the course of experiments (Turner and Pöppel 1988; Biederman 1987). Hence, image structural features as the basis of thinking are also the basis of positive emotions in perception.

Interrelations of structures of sign systems actualized by codes are obvious in various games. In card games, codes connect the seniority of suits, pictures, trump and non-trump cards, possible tricks and leads. In chess, they link colors, checkerboard squares, figures – their positions and leads, into systems. Codes are structure mechanisms of certain relation types as well as structures connecting relation types (for example, systems of figures on board and systems of possible leads). Various structures can also be viewed as translated from some heterogeneities into others. The knots of interacting structures form their universal transformations (Somov 1990). This corresponds to the idea of translation of structures in information processes (Lefebvre 1973 [1967]; Stepanov 1971; Ursul 1971), the ideas of structure transformations as the essence of thinking processes (Voronin et al. 1982), structure transformation into architectural shaping (Barbyshev and Somov 1972, 1976; Somov 1986b, 1990). On the whole, various structural transformations of some heterogeneities into other ones can be regarded as particular

codes – *mechanisms of structural transformations*. The idea of structural transformations is close to the semiotic ideas of codes as double structures, which are grounded on the analysis of the DNA double helix (Hoffmeyer and Emmeche 1991). General ideas of structures spread into the field of philosophical problems of semiotics and other sciences are clearly seen in the arrangement of visual information. The interrelations of certain characteristics, relations, elements of organized structures with certain codes are obvious here. In particular, the relations of object sizes and color relations are actualized in the codes of identifying the distance of these objects from the spectator (Somjen 1972). Structures are actualized in element relations according to certain characteristics. Light-and-shade contrasts are necessary for identifying geometrical shape and forming the idea of light. The contour breaking points are the basis for identification of object classes (animals, plants, objects, people). Hence, objects are recognized by characteristic contour breaks in silhouettes (Fayermark 1974). The features of silhouettes are also essential for identifying motion, actions, intentions, and emotions of animate objects. It is notable that code mechanisms connect the universals of the signifier (features of curves, straight, zigzag lines, size ratios, elements and their location, etc.) and the universals of the signified (characteristics, relations, elements of human figures, animals, objects) in the examples adduced above. Their connections are realized on the basis of structures (structures of size relations, mutual arrangement of elements, moving directions, rhythmical sequences, numbers, etc.).

Features are qualitative characteristics of heterogeneity with relations that form structures and are included in codes. Distinctive features are the basis of important differentiations. They allow referring situations and objects to certain classes of situations and objects and promote efficient actions and behavior in these situations. This fundamental role of differential signs in the regulation and information processes determines their role in languages and cultures. Features are included into codes. The connections of features and codes are manifested in visual perception and organization of visual sign systems in various ways. In particular, distinctive features of configurations – salience and concavity, angularity and roundedness, elongation and compactness, etc. – are the basis of various codes. The given features are connected with calmness and anxiety, statics and dynamics, recognition of living beings, physical phenomena, and others. Feature activity and image heterogeneity foster the realization of codes. Thus, activation of the mentioned features of configurations and their contours promotes identifying figures that are walking or running, calm or aggressive, peaceful or fighting. Strengthening of differences related to light-and-shade enables the formation of the idea of object geometric shape. Geometric features, in their turn, are important for the recognition of heaviness and lightness, stability, and dynamics of the

objects. The features of warm colors foster the senses of warmth and coziness; those of cold colors arouse the senses of open space, cold, and wind. Feature activity is interconnected with differences-identities and their modifications – contrasts and nuances. Strong differences activate the features included in them. Nuances, on the contrary, hinder the realization of these features in codes. The dominant features and their interrelations in differences-identities in the works of visual art reveal the key sign formations and meanings of these works. The dominant color spectrum enables the realization of various codes, signs, meanings. Combined with dominant configurations and forms, it creates more concrete signs and meanings. Thus, the combinations of dynamic forms and bright colors express power and energy; those of amorphous, vague contours and faded colors express uncertainty and infirmity. These meanings can be changed through the change of designates.

Differential features and codes embrace various levels of “the signified – the signifier” relations. Therefore, the features of heterogeneities of the signified (objects and interpretants) are essential in visual art as well as the features of the visual heterogeneity perceived directly. The features of verticals – horizontals are important as the basis of indicating the forces of gravitation, inclination (wind, object moving, etc.). Statics and dynamics, pressure and rise are the signs of the signified of a “higher” level (earthiness, rise, ascension). In particular, wavy rises and splashes mean overcoming force, impulse, and liberation. These designates of the first level, in their turn, are interrelated with designates of the next level (dignity, elation, feeling of freedom, spiritual uplift, etc.). As codes are integrated with each other in various ways, property relations in sign formation are not quite clear. This is connected with various ways of semiosis (Eco 1976) and indefiniteness of visual meanings (Panofsky 1983 [1955]). Naturally, such meanings acquire more certainty in textual sign systems. At the same time, the time of semiosis is of probabilistic nature. The integration of various codes and the probabilistic nature of their realization are characteristic of various levels of the signified and the signifier. The differential signs of “higher” levels of the signified are of more stable nature due to the conditional and definite “the signified – the signifier” connections in verbal sign systems. In particular, diverse features of ethno-cultural communities are of a global generalizing nature. Such characteristics are obvious in architectural motifs, ornament, costume, decorations, whereas in painting they appear as secondary ones. Relative motifs are recognized due the features of configurations. Therefore, stable units are seen in the evolution of ornaments (correlates with language figures by L. Hjelmslev).

Differences-identities are actualized according either to one property or to a group of features. Hence, the techniques based on differences and identities according to various features are seen in the course of image analysis. In particular,

this is obvious in font systems where letter elements are identified. Complicated fonts (gothic, classical, etc.) are read easily due to the identities of separate letter elements and active differences of the general configurations of these letters. In Chinese calligraphy, this correlation is quite the opposite. Here, the identities are preserved merely in general constructions of hieroglyphs while the differences become the field of the signified. Therefore, hieroglyphs acquire an individual, pictorial nature and are painted in various improvisations. The techniques of drawing, graphics, painting (contouring of images by lines of equal thickness, the use of configurations of the same color or similar colors, equal or similar dabs or groups of dabs, strokes in parallel lines in a drawing, etc.) are similar to those of identifying elements in the art of European fonts. Such identities allow for the connecting and intensifying of various codes and signs. In particular, different in size but equal configurations strengthen their features (regularity, bilateral symmetry, elongation, angularity, roundness, etc.). Thus, repetition of face contours in human figure configurations in a portrait enables effective perception and memorizing of the face. It also acquires the meanings expressed actively (strength, strictness, authoritativeness, etc.) largely due to the identity of its configurations and the contours of a human figure, costume, decorations, and other elements. Hence, such identifications were widely used in the art of portrait. Such differences-identities are also essential in the image emotional impact as they are included in the codes of emotive character. The identifications of strong, pulsating lines, restless silhouettes, and active colors are included in the codes in emotional impacts and therefore promote these impacts. Differences-identities organize both the level of visual heterogeneity in visual art and other levels including the systems of semantic elements and relations. Identities-differences of these two different levels are interrelated in the works forming the basis of various codes. In particular, the location of human figures, their heads, figures, hands lower or higher than the horizontals of the picture encodes different significance of the depicted characters or their belonging to different realities. The position of characters' face centers on one and the same line or in a single system of lines singles out identities of these characters according to various semantic features (relationship, group of like-minded people, position in society, etc.). In cultural systems, differences-identities form the basis of social and ideological codes that are referred to as being independent semiotic codes (Chandler 1994).

In stable systematicities of the linguistic type, differences-identities are established due to the establishment of basic codes. And vice versa, differences and identities of vitally important situations and their objects in behavior and activity are materialized in the stable code mechanisms. Vitally important differences-identities (dangerous-safe, troubleshooting-comfort, restricted-free, attractive-

unattractive, kind-evil, elevated-sinister, etc.) are formed. The inter-subjective (common in communication) nature of these differences is confirmed by the coincidence of the results of the method of semantic differential by Osgod.

Features and differences-identities are realized in elements and their groups. Elements can be viewed as localized in time and space, on the one hand, and as knots of features, differences, and identities, their realizations, on the other hand. The latter corresponds to the description of the units of verbal language and speech as well as to identification units in identification theory and methods (Shekhter 1967; Bongard 1967; Fayermark 1974). Due to the identities formed according to differential features, elements are linked with each other and intensified. This is clearly seen in portrait art. The lines and configurations organizing the image (sleeves, collars, cuffs, decorations, etc.) are used in depicting rich clothes of sixteenth century. The lines and configurations of the costume and its details, in their turn, become similar to the ovals and contours of head and face. The author adduced such organizing universals, in particular, in the course of analysis of the *Lady with an Ermine* by Leonardo (Somov 2008). Rafael, H. Holbein the Younger, and some other portrait masters of the Renaissance used similar techniques. These techniques allow activating features and structures due to which identification of the depicted property is carried out. On the whole, such techniques enable the formation of a holistic image of a person. The activity of the elements of visual heterogeneity is interconnected with their activity as semantic elements. In particular, a dark eye surrounded by a light part of the face of a characteristic in a portrait becomes a particularly significant sign and bears great importance. The eye emphasized actively is included in the system of eyes of other characteristics, in the system of representation of their inner states. In general, one can postulate that *groups of elements, their differences and identities, features of differences and identities at various levels are included in the structures that unite them* (signals, representaments, signs, semantic elements).

The knots of code intersections are realized in coding and decoding. These knots are reflected in language sciences, in the theory of image identification as feature bundles (realizations; Shekhter 1967; Fayermark 1974). Correspondingly, code knots – the stable units of various levels – are formed in visual information and art. Preservation of these stable units in paradigmatics is connected with the formation of code relations and features in the bundles. For example, silhouettes of vitally important objects, color and shape combinations create realizations. The mechanisms of relations between the new codes and disintegration (deconstruction of the formed bundles as changes) are formed in human cognitive processes, including visual perception (phylogenesis and ontogenesis). They connect features, differences-identities, all basic universals of heterogeneities,

groups of elements as means of connection, construction principles. Due to its linking role, *the structure* is regarded in various conceptions of structuralism. It would be reasonable to define structures as *construction principles, means of cohesion of parts of a whole* (Toda and Shuford 1965, Il'in 1972). As a means of connection, a structure can: 1) embrace both sign formations proper and signified objects including the objects of physical reality; 2) organize a group of relations and elements as a whole; 3) connect various levels of “the signified – the signifier” (Somov 1986b). In the structure of a whole of a certain level, some multitude of structures realized in element identities formed according to certain features can be singled out. In particular, structures are often opposed and reveal identities, differences and separate features in the elements perceived directly and image relations (Somov 1986a). Thus, horizontal elements of a landscape or slopes close to horizontals form active structures that are opposed to the structure of verticals or inclined lines close to them – trees, building walls, human figures, etc. These structures in their integrity form a more general structure of linear constructions of a landscape. The linear structure is usually opposed to the structures of localized elements – dots and configurations in the images. Structures of these various features and relations can be connected by other structures (general rhythms, symmetries, focus points, axes, proportional size ratios, etc.). Thus, it can be stated that structures link relation and element groups and arrange their heterogeneities for the realization of codes and signs. As structures are realized in various “the signified – the signifier” relations, they are essential at various levels of these relations (construction levels by Paul Garwin): at the levels of signals, signs proper, semantic units. The author aimed to demonstrate these levels in the course of analysis of artworks (Somov 2005) relying on the semiotic models of levels (Prieto 1964; Sharov 1999; Figure 3).

All systems of different levels are related. Therefore a single structure is really perceived. This was shown in visual artworks (Benveniste 1971). Recognizing a single structure and a single visual system that connect all four levels, one can allow the abstract systems and structures of each levels. A single structure integrates differential structures as was demonstrated in the examples (Somov 2005).

Structures of the signal level (1) organize differences – identities on the whole, *visual heterogeneities* of relations – the elements-signals perceived directly.

Actually it is expedient to separate the signs in visual art from representamens. With this distinction, signs have strictly defined the signifieds and the signifiers (figures of human and animals; heads, faces, arms; house wares, etc.). Representamens are indefinite signifieds and signifiers (movements, fluids of energy, forces of attack and defense, structures of depicted space, ghostly figures and things, etc.).

Fig. 3: Heterogeneities and levels of construction. Level of figures (signals) (1), level of representamens (2), level of signs (3), level of units of semantic systems (4). H – heterogeneity, O – object, I – interpretant, R – representamen, S – signal, Sn – sign.

Structures of the representamen levels (2) organize relations of representamens connected in sign systems. But these structures are not essential to the given systems of signs. So some connotations are formed (for example, transparent silhouettes, outlines, and the lines of human figures forming a special layer of an elusive reality of a picture that is the most evident in Brueghel's *Peasant Dance*; Somov 2009).

Structures of the sign level (3) organize sign relations according to the features of representamen heterogeneities. Such are the hierarchical structures (significations) of the depicted objects, static or dynamic structures, moving directions, contrasts of heavy and light objects.

Structures of the level of semantic units (4) unite the objects and interpretants of the given level by common relations. The formation of these structures is reflected in the models of semantic dual structures (Ivanov 2008; Greimas and Courtes 1979). The structures organize the groups of signified objects and interpretants. In particular, characters are evaluated in terms of their interrelations as antipodes: friends and hosts, fighting and allies, etc. The estimates of emotional nature, standards, moral systems, ideals are also characterized by relations (oppositions of heroism and anti-heroism, good and evil, virtue and vice, love and hatred, elevated and sinister, beautiful and ugly, etc.). The determination of the organizing codes by cognitive intentions generates a tendency of the denotative-

cognitive processes to structure the signified in perception processes. Such oppositions established in the models of situations and world pictures including verbal systems are realized in visual information and art. The structures of actions, intentions, and emotional states of the depicted animate characters are singled out at the level of semantic units. The structures of life situations become the key ones at this level. They appear in the basic dichotomies of human existence (the opposition of kind and evil forces, good and bad characters, structures of events and spaces of life, structural features of social groups, state persons, etc.).

The structures of various levels are specifically manifested in the symbolic, imaginary, and real world, in the fundamental pre-language and language systems, languages, discourses, and texts. On the whole, it is necessary to note the difference between the structures of the pointed levels and the fundamentality in the formation, functioning, and development of sign systems. The idea of the structure universal nature corresponds to the widest interpretation of structures in semiotic conceptions as the basis of human thinking, language, culture, psyche in general. It is necessary to ground the ontological status of systems to describe signs in detail on the basis of structure models of various levels.

Systems can be viewed as groups of relations and elements connected by structures. Correspondingly, systems can be singled out on the basis of these or those features and their combinations. This answers the scientific interpretations of interrelations between systems and structures (Toda and Shuford 1965), their description in some semiotic conceptions (Kubryakova and Mel'nikov 1972). Relying on these ideas, one can say that groups of element relations united by structures materialize these structures and are connected by structures into more general sign formations. Sign systems are formed as structures run through them. Codes are mechanisms that link the structures of some heterogeneities with the structures of other heterogeneities. The connection between structures and codes allows regarding various mechanisms of this kind. The structural transformations generating sign systems are viewed below. Here, it is important to point at the specific sign systems appearing in the visual material of the works. The signal level systems (in abstract art) are the most obvious ones. Any plot painting also possesses a "layer" of signals. Therefore, the techniques connected with the activity of the signal layer and its organization can be found in various trends of visual art.

The signified objects and their representamens can be viewed as systems (semes, by L. Prieto). This is clearly seen in the interrelations of the depicted characters – in their mutual location in space and their representamens on surface (mutual location of people in the depicted space and their configurations on surface) – in visual information and art.

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